

Stale seedbed—an alternate technology for preplanting to achieve total weed control in direct-seeded lowland rice

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Direct seeding of rice as a means of crop establishment is now recognized as a viable alternative to transplanting. It uses less labor and is less costly. However, it is constrained by heavy weed infestation, which reduces yield by 15–70%. The system, which now covers 12–14% of wetland rice tracts in Asia, can be sustained only if it is accompanied by an effective and low-cost weed control system that is free of phytotoxicity and pollution of the aquatic system.

The stale seedbed technology generally recommended for raising small grains under weed-free upland conditions can be used in direct-seeded lowland rice as a no-cost, ecofriendly, and energy-efficient weed control method. In this technique, field preparation to puddling and leveling is done as in normal rice culture. The field is then left as it is and is not allowed to dry completely. Weed seeds are allowed to germinate and water is let into the field after 7–10 d to a depth of 10–15 cm and retained for another 7–10 d. All the germinated weed seeds have decayed by this time and pregerminated rice is sown in water at 100 kg ha⁻¹. The field is drained after 12–24 h and rice seedlings come out in a weed-free environment.

A trial was conducted at the Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, India, and in farmers' fields in larger plots for 2 years during the main crop (*Puncha*) season (Oct–Feb). The rice tract was either rainfed or submerged lowland fields comprising 56,000 ha in the

Kuttanad region, lying 0.5–1 m below mean sea level. This region is the rice bowl of the state. This area is representative of deltaic alluvium in river mouths in India and Asia. Land preparation and crop establishment are done after pumping out water from fields. A complete shift from transplanting to direct seeding has taken place in this tract because of labor scarcity and high cost. *Echinochloa stagnina*, *E. crus-galli*, and *Oryza rufipogon*; *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Cyperus iria*, and *C. difformis*; and *Monochoria vaginalis* and *Sphenoclea zeylanica* are the native grasses, sedges, and broadleaf weeds, respectively, associated with rice cropping. Under uncontrolled conditions, yield can decline by 70%.

In the experiment, four treatments were tried in 20-m² plots and replicated thrice. Results pooled over 2 years (Table 1) showed that direct sowing under the stale seedbed system pro-

duced the highest yield, equivalent to that of an almost totally weed-free crop environment. Although statistically similar, both normal wetland sowing and transplanting resulted in lower yields possibly because of initial crop-weed competition. Transplanting in the stale seedbed resulted in a significantly higher weed population and lower yield.

The experiment in the farmers' fields consisted of four treatments, each in larger plots of 600 m² and replicated in three farmers' fields. Observations on weed parameters were collected from twelve 1-m² quadrats in opposite diagonals of each plot. Results (Table 2) showed the significant yield advantage of the stale seedbed system over hand weeding or chemical weed control, at no additional cost. Preemergence application of butachlor significantly damaged rice seedlings and reduced yield by 0.9 t ha⁻¹. The experiment in bigger plots proved

Table 1. Influence of planting system and method of weed control on weed population and rice yield.

Planting system and weed control method	Weed population at 20 DAS ^a (no. m ⁻²)			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Grass	Sedge	Broadleaf weeds	
Direct sowing in stale seedbed	3	4	6	4.6
Transplanting in stale seedbed	26	31	28	3.1
Normal direct sowing—weeded	60	49	41	2.6
Normal transplanting—unweeded	57	51	40	2.7
Normal direct sowing—hand-weeded at 23 DAS	64	48	37	4.3
Normal transplanting—hand-weeded at 23 DAS	58	51	35	4.4
CD (0.05)	8.3	5.3	6.7	0.4
CV	13.5	11.3	12.2	9.1

^aDAS = days after sowing, CD = critical difference, CV = coefficient of variation.

Table 2. Comparison of stale seedbed and conventional methods in terms of crop establishment, weed population, and rice yield.

Weed method control	Crop plants (no. m ⁻² at 18 DAS) ^a	Weeds (no. m ⁻² at 70 DAS)				Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Weed control cost (\$ ha ⁻¹)
		Rice seedlings	Grass	Sedge	Broadleaf weeds		
Hand-weeded at 23 DAS	206	81	68	31	4	5.6	60.00
Unweeded	211	73	59	36	7	2.4	0
Preemergence application of butachlor at 0.8 kg ai ha ⁻¹ at 5 DAS	174	14	8	6	6	5.2	17.50
Stale seedbed	201	2	4	7	0	6.1	0
CD (0.05)	9.1	8.7	9.4	6.4	2.3	0.5	
CV	6.7	10.9	13.2	12.7	34.7	11.5	

^aDAS = days after sowing, CD = critical difference, CV = coefficient of variation.

the adaptability of the stale seedbed system in farmers' fields. Results clearly showed that the stale seedbed is a no-cost, weed-con-

trol, productivity-facilitating system. Yield improvement over other systems is due to the direct effect of organic transformation of

the soil environment and to efficient weed control. The stale seedbed system is also an effective tool to improve the quality of crop production in areas where wild rice is a problem.

The stale seedbed is not effective in a manually transplanted system, however, because of the emergence of secondary weed flushes as a result of soil disturbances. The minimal soil disturbance in using a mechanical transplanter is expected to make the stale bed system widely adaptable in countries such as Japan and Korea, where transplanting is mainly done using a transplanter.

Influence of long-term crop management practices on grain yield and incidence of brown planthopper in rice

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A correct ratio between organic and inorganic sources of nutrients is essential to ensure optimum yield in any crop, including rice. A long-term experiment to study the influence of organic and inorganic nutrient sources on rice yield started in the 1991 kharif season at ARS, Siruguppa, in the Tungabhadra project area of Karnataka, India. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications at a fixed site. Different levels of inorganic fertilizers (NPK), organic sources (farmyard manure, *Gliricidia*, *Sesbania*), and plant population were included as treatments (see table). A common dose of zinc (at 20 kg ha⁻¹) in the form of zinc sulfate was ap-

plied to all treatments. Rice variety BPT-5204 was planted every kharif season at 20 × 10-cm spacing, except in treatments where 25% more seedlings were transplanted, which used a spacing of 15 × 10 cm. Brown planthopper (BPH) was recorded in the 1999 kharif season 90 d after transplanting (DAT) on 10 hills in each treatment and computed per hill. Both grain yield and BPH population data were subjected to statistical analysis.

The BPH population varied significantly among treatments even though lower pest incidence occurred during the 1999 kharif season (see table). The variation would have been more pronounced if the BPH population

buildup had been high. The BPH population was significantly higher in treatments T9 and T10, which received more nutrients from both inorganic and organic sources. The higher amount of N applied in T9, coupled with more plant population (T10), resulted in a higher BPH population. Hence, caution must be exercised when giving advice on applying higher N doses. The highest grain yield during the 1999 kharif season was recorded in T10 (6.5 t ha⁻¹) and was on a par with T3 (6.2 t ha⁻¹), T4 (6.3 t ha⁻¹), T7 (6.0 t ha⁻¹), T8 (6.4 t ha⁻¹), and T9 (6.3 t ha⁻¹). Applying 100:50:50:20 kg NPKZn ha⁻¹ as only inorganic fertilizer (T1) resulted in lower grain yield and BPH population